

ISic3225

I.Sicily inscription 3225

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 980

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [D(is)M(anibus)s(acrum)]

2. C(ai) · C[o][---]

3. Magn[ivix(it)]

4. an(nis) II me[ns(ibus)---]

5. VII[] Çis[s][us---]

6. et Cra[---]

7. nepoti[---]

8. mo

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

[Sacred to the shades of the underworld(?)] Caius Co... Magnus lived for 2 years, [8-9] months. Cissus and Cra...[built this].

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285114

EDR 121259

EDCS 9600754

Bibliography

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At no.26

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